

The Role of Customer Trust and Satisfaction in Technology Acceptance Model

(A survey of small and medium size enterprises of furniture and handicrafts in Yogyakarta, Indonesia)

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Abstract:

The aim of this paper is to investigate the impact of individual dimensions of Online Service Quality on perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, customer satisfaction, trust and loyalty in e-commerce settings. Empirical results indicate that the perceived service quality has positive direct effects on both customer satisfaction and trust. The results also show that customer satisfaction appears to have a positive direct effect on trust, while both customer satisfaction and trust have direct positive effects on loyalty through satisfaction and trust. Thus, both satisfaction and trust play an imperative role in creating customer loyalty as suggested by many authors. Some theoretical and managerial implications and suggestions for future research are also provided.

Keywords: Online Service Quality, perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, customer satisfaction, trust, loyalty, e-commerce setting, Indonesia

INTRODUCTION

With the continuing growth of the Internet, various researchers have examined such differential effects as perception, attitude, and behavioral changes on the online, so-called virtualized and computer-mediated environment (Hoffman and Novak, 1996) compared to the offline environment, called the marketplace.

In light of these considerations, the purpose of this study is to explore the factors that influence behavioral intentions in a certain context to shop on the Internet. The core constructs of the framework are adapted from the well-known Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) by Davis (1989), one of the most influential extensions of Ajzen and Fishbein's Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and has been proven to be suitable as a theoretical foundation for the adoption of e-commerce by numerous researchers (Chen, Gillenson, & Sherrel, 2002; Moon & Kim, 2001; Lederer, Maupin, Sena, & Zhuang, 2000; Agarwal & Jayesh, 1999; Gefen & Detmar, 1997; Adams, 1992). This study addresses the main research question, "What drives consumers to shop online?" In particular, this study examines i) the effects of factors perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness on satisfaction and trust; ii) the effects of satisfaction on trust, iii) the effects of trust on e-loyalty drawing from Indonesian SMEs (Small and medium-sized enterprises) customers handicraft and furniture in Yogyakarta.

Loyal customers are indeed crucial to business survival (Reichheld and Scheffer 2000, Semejin et al. 2005). For that reason many companies use defensive marketing strategies to increase their market share and profitability by maximizing customer retention (Tsoukatos and Rand 2006). Although traditionally, more efforts are dedicated to offensive strategies (Fornell 1992), research has shown that defensive strategies can be more profitable through increased cross-selling, possibly at higher prices, and positive word-of mouth (WOM) communication. In an e-commerce setting, at its highest level, companies can use the Internet to deliver products and services to their customers. They can have mutually rewarding relationships with customers they have never seen, met, or spoken to. The entire relationship can successfully exist in cyberspace. Leveraging the Internet can free up resources to deliver higher levels of value to customers in new ways. The Internet provides companies and consumers with opportunities for much greater interaction and individualization. Indeed, perceived service quality and customer satisfaction are dominating the marketing literature.

However, the relationships between the two constructs are debatable (Brown and Swartz 1989, Carman 1990, Cronin and Taylor 1992, 1994). Clearly, all companies need to consider and evaluate e-marketing and e-purchasing opportunities. A key challenge is designing a site that is attractive on first viewing and interesting enough to encourage repeat visits. Moreover, customers are becoming more open to competitive advances and are more familiar with brands and thus, satisfaction alone may not be adequate to ensure long-term customer commitment to a single online service provider (Heskett et al. 1994, Ranaweera and Prabhu 2003). Online companies often look beyond satisfaction to developing trust in order to reduce the perceived risk of using the service. Perhaps, trust is also seen as being a critical factor of considerable importance in the process of building and maintaining relationships in online services (Corbitt et al. 2003, Gummerus et al. 2004, Reichheld and Scheffer 2000, Ribbink et al. 2004, Semejin et al. 2005). Companies also face challenges in expanding the public use of e-commerce. Customers will have to feel that the information that they supply is confidential and not to be sold to others. They will need to trust that online transactions are secured. Research suggests that up to 75% of online shoppers do not complete their purchase on the Internet. Instead they use e-commerce sites to find and research products or services before completing their purchase either by phone or with a visit to a physical store (Anderson and Kerr 2002). The theoretical background and the empirical support for these issues come mostly from developed countries.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Attitudes and behavioral intentions toward the online environment have been widely supported by the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989). Earlier studies of e-commerce considered how customers adopt the technology in a computer-mediated environment. To change perceptions in e-commerce, studies addressed customers' willingness to change attitudes and behaviors by focusing on ease of use and usefulness (Davis, 1989) - key variables in the TAM. Technology acceptance has been a prominent research stream in information systems for over two decades, with the TAM and the primary constructs of perceived ease of use (EOU), perceived usefulness (U), and behavioral intention (BI) (Davis, 1989; Davis, Bagozzi, and Warshaw, 1989; cited in Hess, McNab, and Basoglu, 2014). The first determinant is perceived usefulness, defined as the individual's perception that using the new technology will enhance or improve her or his performance (Davis, 1989; Davis, Bagozzi, and Warshaw, 1989). The second determinant - perceived ease of use - refers to the extent to which a person believes that using the new technology will be free of effort (Davis, 1989; Davis, Bagozzi, and Warshaw, 1989). While perceived usefulness refers to consumers' perceptions regarding the outcome of the experience, perceived ease of use refers to their perceptions regarding the process leading to the final outcome (Monsuwe, Dellaert, & Ruyter, 2004). The TAM has been tested and validated by numerous researchers and shown to be suitable as a theoretical foundation for the adoption of e-commerce (Chen, Gillenson, & Sherrel, 2002; Moon & Kim, 2001; Lederer, Maupin, Sena, & Zhuang, 2000; Agarwal & Jayesh, 1999; Gefen & Detmar, 1997; Adams, 1992).

Perceived usefulness (Davis, 1989) is defined here as "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance." This follows from the definition of the word useful: "capable of being used advantageously." Within an organizational context, people are generally reinforced for good performance by raises, promotions, bonuses, and other rewards (Pfeffer, 1982; Schein, 1980; Vroom, 1964). A system high in perceived usefulness, in turn, is one for which a user believes in the existence of a positive use-performance relationship.

Perceived ease of use (Davis, 1989), in contrast, refers to "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free of effort." This follows from the definition of "ease": "freedom from difficulty or great effort." Effort is a finite resource that a person may allocate to the various activities for which he or she is responsible (Radner and Rothschild, 1975). All else being equal, we claim, an application perceived to be easier to use than another is more likely to be accepted by users.

Trust is an important construct catalyst in many transactional relationships. For example, in the commitment-trust relationship marketing literature, trust has been conceptualized as existing when one party has confidence in a partner's reliability and integrity (Morgan and Hunt 1994, Ranaweera and Phrabu 2003). Indeed, trust could exist at the individual level (Rotter 1967) or at the firm level (Moorman et al. 1993). Furthermore, trust when conceptualized as a dimension of technology acceptance model (TAM), could have a striking influence on user willingness to engage in online exchanges of money and personal sensitive information as well (e.g. Friedman et al. 2000, Hoffman et al. 1999, Wang et al. 2003). Thus, perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness may not fully reflect the users' intention to adopt Internet banking (Eriksson et al. 2005, Wang et al. 2003). On the other hand, in the service quality literature, trust could also be thought as 'trust in the service itself' (Parasuraman et al. 1985, 1988). Such a relationship is crucial to managing trust, because a customer typically must buy a service before experiencing it. Also, the existence of trust in a relationship is a kind of insurance against risks and unexpected behavior. Trust partly depends on experience from interacting with another party. For example, a customer who has been doing business with a service provider for some time and is pleased with the results is inclined to trust that service provider.

Many authors considered trust as an outcome of customer satisfaction and as an antecedent of customer commitment and customer loyalty (Moorman et al. 1993). According to Gronroos (2001) trust towards a system depends not only on the laws, industry regulations and contracts but also on the professionalism of the other party. If a customer, for example, has entered into a long-term contract with a service provider, the customer trusts that the service provider will perform according to expectations.

Trust is seen as being of considerable importance in the process of building and maintaining relationships, although it is also recognized as being difficult to manage (Bejou et al. 1998). In a research on online banking customers, Mukherjee and Nath (2003) looked at trust as a driver of customer relationship commitment. They found that trust has a significant positive influence on relationship commitment. Another positive effect of trust on customer loyalty with respect to the service provider has been demonstrated by Gefen (2002) for an online vendor. In line with these findings, when a customer trusts an online vendor s/he is expected to increase loyalty towards that vendor. At the same time, it decreases the perceived risk with the online vendor as well. Although many authors suggested that trust is directly affecting loyalty but its anticipated contribution to loyalty is much less than to satisfaction (see Ribbink et.al. 2004).

Customer satisfaction is how satisfied a customer is with the supplied product/service. It is closely related to interpersonal trust [Geyskens, Steenkamp, Scheer, and Kumar 1996]

In line with earlier research [Zins, 2001], it is expected that a higher level of customer satisfaction will lead to greater loyalty. However, the impact of satisfaction on customer loyalty is rather complex. Fisher [2001] believes that customer satisfaction accounts for only part of why people change product or service providers. Other studies have shown that customer satisfaction is a leading factor in determining loyalty [Anderson and Lehmann 1994]. Anderson and Srinivasan [2003] found that both trust and perceived value, as developed by the company, significantly accentuate the impact of satisfaction on e-commerce loyalty. In a more recent study by Cyr [2008] it was found that website satisfaction is strongly related to loyalty in three countries: Canada, Germany, and China.

Generally, loyalty has been defined as the repeat purchasing frequency or the relative volume of same-brand purchasing. Oliver [1997] defines customer loyalty as a deeply held commitment to re-buy or re-patronize a preferred product/service consistently in the future, thereby causing repetitive same brand or same brand set purchasing, despite situational influences and marketing efforts having the potential to cause switching behavior. In e-commerce, loyal customers are considered extremely valuable. Today, e-retailers are seeking information on how to build customer loyalty. Loyal customers not only require more information themselves, but they serve as an information source for other customers. Building customer loyalty is one of the biggest challenges for B2C e-commerce.

Several antecedents of customer loyalty have been proposed. Customer satisfaction and trust have been brought forward as a precondition for patronage behavior [Pavlou 2003] and the development of long-term customer relationships [Papadopoulou, Andreou, Kanellis, and Martakos, 2001]. The study by Kassim and Ismail [2009] found that services quality and vendor's assurance to online customers in Qatar, contribute to building trust and satisfaction thereby improving customer loyalty.

Methodology

3.1. Research Model

Figure 1 depicts the research model employed in the study. It is an extended TAM model. In this model, portal usage is predicted by one's trust in this portal. Trust in the portal is predicted by both perceived usefulness and satisfaction in the portal; the former also influences satisfaction in the portal, and satisfaction in the portal is also predicted by perceived ease of use. Perceived ease of use influences both perceived usefulness and satisfaction in the portal.

Figure 1. Technology Acceptance Model

Finally, the perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use are predicted by the Online Service Quality (OSQ), including information content, customization, reliability and response, and security. In this study, the model hypothesizes that the degree that portal site is easy to use, as perceived by students, affects both their perception of the usefulness of the portal site and their satisfaction the portal and e-loyalty portal use in general. We formulate our hypothesis as shown below:

- [H1] There is a positive relationship between online service quality and perceived usefulness of using the portal site.
- [H2] There is a positive relationship between online service quality and perceived ease of use of using the portal site.
- [H3] There is a positive relationship between perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness of using the portal site.
- [H4] There is a positive relationship between perceived ease of use and satisfaction the portal site.
- [H5] There is a positive relationship between perceived usefulness and satisfaction the portal site.
- [H6] There is a positive relationship between perceived usefulness and trust the portal site.
- [H7] There is a positive relationship between satisfaction and trust the portal site.
- [H8] There is a positive relationship between trust and e-loyalty the portal site.

3.2. Research Design

To address this study, a field survey was sent to 450 undergraduate students, who came from six different Management Colleges. All of these students have gotten the credit of the basic computer concepts. The purpose of this

survey investigated the intention of the subjects to their *primary* portal site usage. The 433 complete surveys constitute a 96% response rate.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of respondents' characteristics

Measure	Items	Frequency	%
Gender	Female	256	40.6
	Male	176	59.1
Degree of internet experience	<1 year	65	15
	1-3 years	200	46.2
	3-5 years	121	27.9
	>5 years	47	10.9
Primary use portal site	OLX	314	72.5
	Lazada	29	6.7
	Kaskus	24	5.5
	Bukalapak	28	6.5
	Instagram	17	3.9
	Others	21	4.8
Time of Use primary portal site (everyday)	<1hour	254	58.7
	1-3hours	143	33.0
	3-6hours	26	6.0
	6-9hours	7	1.6
	>9hours	3	0.7
Primary activity	Search data	192	44.3
	Use email	123	28.4
	Read	68	15.7
	news/magazine	50	11.6
	Others		

In selecting the sampling frame, there are three major reasons. First, a survey made by MIC 2000 [26] reported that students hold a 40% proportion of the Internet population; further, 70% of the Internet users education is in the college/university level. Second, students group is in fact the “active users” in the Internet. And third, choosing students as our sampling frame can reduce the variance of the computer knowledge. Detailed descriptive statistics relating to the respondents' characteristics are shown in Table 1.

3.3. Validity and Reliability of Questionnaire

The constructs “perceived ease of use”, “perceived usefulness”, “satisfaction portal site”, “behavior intention to reuse portal site”, and “actual portal site use” were referenced from Davis [6] and Davis et al. [8], Lin & Lu [24], Leaderer et al. [23]. As for the construct of online service quality were referenced by DeLone & McLean [9], Hoffman et al. [17], PZB [30,32]. Further, for a complete consideration of the face validity and content validity of this questionnaire, six Ph.D. students were first examined and forty-one undergraduate students were asked to test for pilot test. The construct validity is categorized into convergence and discriminant validity. Convergence validity means that evidence from different sources gathered in different ways all indicates the same or similar meaning of the construct. Discriminant validity means that one can empirically differentiate the construct from other constructs that may be similar, and that one can point out what is unrelated to the construct. To test discriminant validity, a principal components factor analysis with varimax rotation for the proposed construct of the online service quality yielded four distinct factors: information content, customization, reliable and response, and security. All four items loaded on a distinct factor. Factor loadings for all variables were greater than 0.5 [21]. Together, the three observed factors accounted for 75.93 percent of the total variance. In this study, bartlett’s test of sphericity (p-value=0.000) indicates that the statistical probability that the correlation matrix has significant correlation among at least some of the variables, and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy (0.928) show high sampling adequacy [13]. The convergent validity is based on the idea that items are valid measures of the same concept should correlate rather highly with one another or yield similar results even though they are different instruments. Therefore, the correlations provide evidence that the items all converge on the same construct, and the correlation is significant at the 0.01 level [21]. Internal consistency was assessed by computing Cronbach’s alpha. In this study, the values range from 0.73 to 0.89 with nine constructs [29]. The intent of our study was to extend TAM by adding an online service quality concept in the portal site context. We hoped to explain user acceptance of the portal site. The research model and hypotheses were tested using path analysis. In this study, path analysis was undertaken using structural equation modeling (SEM) techniques. The SEM technique used in this study was LISREL (Linear Structural Relations). Fit indices reported in LISREL to identify goodness of fit include: (1) the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)(greater than 0.9); (2) GFI Adjusted for Degree of Freedom (AGFI) (greater than 0.8); (3) Root Mean Square Residual (RMSR)(less than 0.10); (4) the Comparative Fit Index (CFI)(greater than 0.9); (5) the Normed Fit Index (NFI) (greater than 0.9); (6) a Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI)(greater than 0.9); and (7) chi-square/degree of freedom (less than 5) [20]. Figure 2 shows the results of SEM analysis of the path model developed in this study. This study was close enough to suggest that the model fit was reasonably adequate to assess the results for the structural model. The explanatory power of the model for

individual constructs was examined using the resulting R2 for each dependent construct. Together, information content, customization, reliability & response and perceived ease of use were able to explain 53 percent of the variances observed in perceived usefulness. At the same time, the combination of information content, customization, reliability & response were accounted for 31 percent of the variances observed in perceived ease of use. Perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use were able to explain 29 percent of the variances observed in Internet users' satisfaction portal site. Meanwhile, the combination of perceived usefulness of and satisfaction portal site accounted for 55 percent of the variances observed in the Internet users' intention to use the portal site. Finally, the intention to use the portal site of Internet users' was able to explain 26 percent of the variances observed in e-loyalty use the portal site.

Figure 2. Results of LISREL testing

Hypotheses 1 and 2 examine the links between online service quality (information content, customization, reliability & response, and security) of portal site and perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use: information content is significantly positive related with perceived usefulness ($\beta=0.33$, t -value=6.38, $p<0.01$) and perceived ease of use ($\beta=0.37$, t -value=7.33, $p<0.01$). Customization of portal is significantly positive related with perceived usefulness ($\beta=0.15$, t -value=2.90, $p<0.01$) and perceived ease of use ($\beta=0.18$, t -value=3.54, $p<0.01$). Reliability & response is significantly positive related with perceived usefulness ($\beta=0.09$, t -value=1.73, $p<0.01$) but with non-significant related to perceived ease of use. As for the security of portal is both with non-significant related to the perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Therefore, hypotheses 1 and 2 were partial not rejected. Hypotheses 3 to 8 examine the original TAM's causal model. Also hypothesis 3 was supported ($\beta=0.33$, t -value=5.39, $p<0.01$). Hypothesis 4 was supported ($\beta=0.81$, t value=4.83, $p<0.01$). Hypothesis 5 was supported ($\beta=0.31$, t -value=9.07, $p<0.01$). Hypothesis 6 was supported ($\beta=0.24$, t -value=3.69, $p<0.01$). Hypothesis 7 was supported ($\beta=0.55$, t -value=7.82, $p<0.01$). Hypothesis 8 was supported ($\beta=0.51$, t -value=8.85, $p<0.01$).

4. Discussion

This study examines the TAM model in the Internet environment by adding online service quality of WWW as external variables. Based on data collected from 433 college students, who are all Internet users, the utility of TAM for explaining acceptance of portal site by Internet users was evaluated. The results suggested the general adequacy and applicability of TAM in the portal as indicated by fairly reasonable goodness-of-fit indexes for the model. The study has provided some valuable insight into the Internet user's acceptance of a portal site from the perspectives of online service quality. We have also tested the descriptive validity of TAM in the domain of WWW environment. Based on the above results presented herein, which seem to provide the following implications.

First, the finding of this study shows that the technology acceptant behavior in the voluntary usage environment (e.g., Internet) can be predicted by using TAM. Second, while perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use were both found to have significant influence on intention to reuse the portal site, the data showed that the standardized path coefficients of perceived usefulness to attitude is 0.33 while perceived ease of use to satisfaction portal is 0.81, respectively. Inconsistent with what Davis [30] had postulated in his study that perceived usefulness is more important than perceived ease of use, the finding of this study showed that the perceived ease of use (0.81) is more significant twice than perceived usefulness (0.33). Concerning about this contrary finding, we may ascribe the difference as a novel finding, since the portal site have its unique property, such as that it is in fact located in the Internet which belongs to a voluntary usage environment; on the contrast, the previous studies used TAM in the task-oriented environment, for instance, the word processors, spreadsheets, etc. The different motivation for users to use the technology would make up the differences. With different traits with the functional information systems, the portal site needs to first pursue the ease of use in order to attract Internet users to visit the portal once again, such as easy target the information they want. This means if a portal site equips with all kinds of services without ease to use,

generally speaking, users will not visit this portal again. Thus, for this novel finding that perceived ease of use is more significant important than the perceived usefulness, we then suggest the companies who already have or are planning to construct one, they need to focus on the design of "ease of use". In this connection, providing proper online manual page (including search tips, benefits of the portal site, why use the portal site, FAQ, and special features, etc.) for users is essential for directing and solidifying users' perceptions of the ease of use of the portal site. Since perceived ease of use is still the primary concern for using a portal, the perceived usefulness of a portal site, however, has indirect effect on the formation of intentions. That is, the easier a portal site is to use, the more usefulness it is perceived to be. Therefore, to promote user's intention to reuse a portal site, the company should promote the portal site's ease more than its usefulness. Increasing the usefulness of a portal site alone might not have increased the user's intention to revisit the site. Third, the online service quality is very important factor in leading people to believe in the usefulness and ease of use that portal site. According to Fig.3, there is both a direct positive effect of online service quality perceived usefulness and on perceived ease of use. Besides the security in the antecedents to the portal is not effect perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. The portal site that provides better online service quality would result in a greater perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use from the user. And finally, attitude was found to be significant in influencing intention to reuse the portal site. This suggests the relative importance of attitude in users' acceptance of portal site and its respective contribution in predicting behavior intention.

5. Conclusion

Theory testing has become increasingly important for IS research [14], and therefore examination or validation of existing findings of user technology acceptance is desirable, or even essential, particularly when different technologies, user populations, or organizational contexts are involved. This study examined TAM using Internet users' acceptance of portal site. Based on data collected from 433 students of college with use portal site experience in Indonesia, the utility of TAM for explaining acceptance of portal site by Internet users' was evaluated. The results suggested the general adequacy and applicability of TAM in this Internet users' context as indicated by fairly reasonable goodness-of-fit indexes for the model. Several implications can be drawn from the findings of the study. First, an important contribution to user technology acceptance research is the use of a preeminent intention-based model in an Internet context; also, the technology acceptant behavior in the voluntary usage environment (e.g., Internet) can be predicted by using TAM. Here, we tested the plausible extension of the applicability of TAM and we contributed the theory-testing efforts to validate research results. Second, this study has also contributed by applying TAM to lay the groundwork for understanding antecedent (information content, customization, reliability & response) to perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. The understanding of them could guide both portal site research and business practices. In conclusion, the findings of this study reveal that, in order to foster user intentions to use portal site, it is important to encourage and cultivate a positive satisfaction the portal site. In this connection, positive perception of the portal ease of use is crucial, whereas the portal usefulness may not be equally important for professional users.

6. Limitation and Future Work

Since the collected data in this study showed that among the 433 valid surveys, 72.5% of the subjects indicated that "Olx" would be their primary portal site, and the other 27.5% are used to visit other sites such as "Lazada", "Kaskus", etc. The survey in this study is also consistent with the investigation Olx itself made; they reported "Olx is the most-visited.

Finally, once the students accumulated the more Internet experience, they will eventually become the more active Internet users and influential consumers in the Internet marketplace after they graduated. Thus, understanding the needs and preferences of potential customers are important and desirable. 1998, pp.757-759.

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